

QUANTITATIVE ASSESSMENT OF THE DETECTION OF DEFECTS BY THERMOGRAPHIC INSPECTION IN VIBRATION MACHINERY MODE

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1 General Introduction

Through past decades, non-destructive inspection technology has been widely used and its leveraging range is continuously growing trend. Recently, quantitative inspection for machinery equipments and facilities with shock or vibrations with rotating have been required and the application of infrared thermograph technology as a useful measurement tool for its own heat dissipations was useful, in which a non-destructive testing (NDT) as a passive infrared thermography was applied.[1] Since infrared thermographic technology with high performances in sensitivity and resolution could scan a large area at the same time as one of non-destructive tastings, this infrared technology extended its applications including to detect cracks, delamination of defects.

Also, as a methodology of faults monitoring with several advantages such as real-time detection and remote detection, it could be applied into the area of automotive, aerospace industry and nuclear plants. At these days, the applications of infrared applications were quickly expanded to the field of fault detection techniques and its utilizations of condition monitoring for the diagnosis were widely increased [2].

In this study, using the infrared thermography method for the diagnosis of ball during operation, evaluation of fault detection was carried out by experiments.

2 Principle of Experimental Configurations

2.1 Thermographic Concepts

Thermographic NDT techniques have been used in a variety of applications, e.g. the inspection of subsurface defects and features, the identification of thermo-physical properties and the detection of coating thickness and hidden structures. In the 1980s, Vavilov and Taylor[2] discussed the principles of thermal NDT, describing its ability to provide quantitative information about hidden defects or features in a material.[3, 4]

When the material includes voids or pores in its structure, its thermal conductivity and density decrease, and the thermal diffusivity is altered, so the conduction of heat through the material is affected. Unlike ESPI, Thermography measures the surface temperature of an object; the temperature difference between the defect and the sound part indicates the size and location of the defect. In this we have used an IR camera (model Silver 450M by Cedip Corp.).

2.2 Loading Conditions of Vibration Modes

An experiment was performed by using B6004, B6204, and B6304 as the test piece. B60XX series are the most widely used in the insulation deep groove ball bearing.[5-7] Fig.s' 1 and 2 show the schematic diagram for the standard of ball bearing and the thermography system used in this experiment, respectively, respectively.

From Fig. 2, it indicates the simple device configuration used in this experiment. The bearing B6304 and housing were installed between a power and a measuring bearing in order to simple support.

Fig. 1 Schematic of deep groove ball bearing

Fig. 2 Rotation laboratory device

2.3 Experimental Configurations

In the shape of bearing used in the general body of revolution, the condition of experiment was assumed as the normality, loss of lubricating oil and spalling state.[8-9] And then the temperature characteristics were observed during the experiment. By using the APM - SC08 ADK Servo Motor of 1HP on 800W, the experiment was performed in 1000, 2000, 3000rpm, respectively.

Table 1 Specifications and dimensions of ball bearing (unit: mm)

Bearing Name	Outer Diameter	Inner Diameter	Ball Number
B6004	42	20	9
B6204	47	20	8
B6304	52	20	7

3 Experimental Results

The infrared thermographic inspection was conducted by using the realwave analyzer and accelerometer. Table 1 shows the result of the experiment. As the result of experiment, it was generated that it made the high sound pressure in 0 ~ 6,000Hz band and the tendency to be more and more decreased by the high frequency over time. And, the experiment were performed until the equilibrium temperature after the temperature rose. 50 frame per a second was measured.

From the experimental results of Fig. 3, quantitative detection was carried out under the speed of 1,000rpm, 2,000rpm, 3,000rpm as normal condition, lubricating oil loss condition, and spalling condition of B6004, B6204 and B6304 ball bearings.

Fig. 3 The result of measurement of B6204

(a) B6204 1,000rpm

(b) B6204 2,000rpm

(c) B6204 3,000rpm

Fig. 4 The result of infrared thermography method of B6204

As shown in Figs of 3, the images obtained from the results of the experiment with B6204. In the correlation of the color come out in an image, temperature is high as it comes close to the red and low as it comes close to the blue.

In Figs of 4, each figure shows quantitative assessment of the infrared thermographic diagnosis method research and the result was analyzed thoroughly. However, this problem was solved by applying the infrared thermography technology which has benefits at non-contact and scanning method. From these figures, each experimental method was applied to the bearing type of B6304. Also, these results of the other bearing came out with this, similarly.

4 Conclusions

In this research, the faults from machinery with vibration mode was measured by using the infrared thermography technology. Also, the thermography displayed by the real-time temperature image was distinguished.

In addition, when measuring with the existing method of diagnosis, it's possible to know only about there is damage or not, but it's difficult to investigate exact damaged parts for the bearing.

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